

Practical applications of isotherapy in chronic and acute pathologies

LUCIANO DI NEPI, MD

The purpose of this monograph is to re-evaluate a powerful homœopathic therapy somehow forgotten in recent years.

Conventional practitioners who give some attention to this very old technique may change their attitude towards homœopathy and together with the younger homœopaths will discover at their disposal a very powerful and rapid-acting form of therapy for, in particular, chronic pathologies where homœopathy has been accused of being rather slow or completely ineffective.

In France, where isotherapy is reimbursed by the social security system, it is extensively used. The French Pharmacopœia defines it as follows: 'Isotherapy is a biotherapy; therefore all remedies must be obtained from substances of microbic composition, secretion or excretions, animal tissues or vegetable elements or allergenic substances'. These are the sources utilized for the various preparations. French legislation prohibits dilutions below the 3CH.

Isotherapy may be divided in two main categories:

- Auto-isotherapy: when the source is obtained directly from the patient (urine, blood, nose, throat, vaginal and conjunctival swabs, pus, skin scales etc.)
- Hetero-isotherapy: when the source is external to the patient (dust, pollens, different foods, microscopical fungi and so on).

History

The veterinarian Guillaume Lux (1773–1847), a contemporary of Hahnemann, applied isotherapy in 1820 for the first time on 'morva', an epidemic infection of animals, with great success. Later Hering used the secretion of human scabies (*Psorinum*) for the therapy of the same disease.

The first to use isotherapy as it is practised today were the German Stapf and the French priest Rev. Collet; but for mysterious reasons

isotherapy was then somehow neglected up to the beginning of the 20th century when two French ENT specialists, Dr Lamasson and Dr Cavanon, re-applied the method in chronic ear and throat infection with remarkable success when compared to the conventional treatments of the time.

The modern homœopath cannot, however, nowadays ignore other therapies of practical use. In the applications of isotherapy there are three general rules that should be observed.

- 1 *Isotherapy is rarely used alone.* It is generally complementary to any homœopathic and/or conventional treatment: both will gain from it, the former with a better and deeper action, the latter in that the length and dosage of conventional medication is reduced.
- 2 *The best results are obtained in chronic infections.* Antibiotics have reduced the use of isotherapy in these cases but if there is no immediate danger it may be applied even in acute cases. The sources collected in the acute phase of the disease and stored, as mother tinctures in the acute phases of the disease, are of great help to prepare isotherapy for recurrences.
- 3 *Isotherapy is generally given in low and medium dilutions.* Even if isotherapy may be considered as a nosode *sui generis*, previous experience and my own experience demonstrate that the best results are obtained beginning from 4c to 21c. In the future it is my intention to experiment with higher dilutions.

Dilutions and their use

I personally use the 4c, 2 pilules daily, 6 days per week with a tube dose one day per week—starting with the 5c in the first week, 7c the second week and 9, 12, 15, 17 and 21c in successive weeks.

Specimen collection

- Antibiotics should be discontinued at least 48 hours before collection, as well as any other

conventional treatments if this can be done without risk.

- Sterile tubes and swabs are advisable but not indispensable.
- In temperate climate, specimens are better preserved without refrigeration and may be mailed if the mailing services of the country are reasonably efficient.
- Mouth washes and vaginal douches should be stopped at least 24 hours before collection of swabs.
- Urine is rarely collected during menstrual periods, for obvious reasons.
- Depending upon the disease, any mixture may be made: dust, plants, pollens, skin scales, food, etc., together with urine, obtaining a combination of hetero- and auto-isotherapy.
- Physiological solutions can replace the urine, but best results are generally obtained with urine.

Some representative cases

Bronchiectasis

B.P., female, aged 36

Since childhood recurrent bronchitis with and without fever. Several chest X-rays taken in past years showed bronchitis only. After three pregnancies sudden onset of severe dyspnoea and recurrent fever. Admitted to hospital, bilateral bronchography demonstrated bilateral congenital saccular bronchiectasis. No surgical therapy was advised and the patient was discharged with antibiotic treatment rotating from kanamycin, erythromycin, ampicillin, cephalosporin, etc., with no improvement in fever and morning mucopurulent sputum; general condition was severely compromised, especially effort dyspnoea. In May 1988 the patient was treated with isotherapy (sputum + urine) (2 cycles), leading to fewer recurrences of fever, increased appetite and reduction of morning sputum from 400 to 200–250ml. At the beginning of the cold season the fever recurred, therefore isotherapy was given in association with cotrimoxazole. The improvement was remarkable. The fever disappeared, sputum reduced to 50–100ml/24 h, clear. Dyspnoea reduced to a minimum, enough to allow the patient to resume work. After one year observation on continuous treatment the condition appears to be stable. ESR and WBC have reverted to normal values.

Psoriasis

P.R., female, age 34

No major disease on past history except frequent tonsillitis and bronchitis from the age of 5 to 10. Treated with several courses of antibiotics. At the age of 9 acne rosacea that subsided after menarche. Age of 23, 1 pregnancy. After starting contraceptive, onset of severe diffuse psoriasis and weight gain for which condition all treatments were refused.

On first examination: weight 63 kg, height 158 cm, BP 130/80. Severe exfoliative psoriasis, mild iatrogenic hypothyroidism confirmed by thyroid function tests.

Treatment: Low calorie diet = 1000 Kcal/24 hours, low fat, sugar free, high protein.

Started on liothyronine.

Isotherapy: Urine during menstrual period + skin scales.

After 45 days, weight 53 kg, skin free from lesions except few residual on knees and elbow. After 5th course of isotherapy the patient maintained her body weight and residual psoriasis lesions completely disappeared. The success in this case when compared to others is probably due to the fact that no conventional treatment was attempted.

Renal and prostatic calculi

P.F., male, age 58

Past history: No major surgery. Age 30 viral pneumonia. Age 35 onset of articular pains (knees, hands, feet), treated for 2 years as acute rheumatic fever without improvement.

Urine and blood test were suggestive of gout and hyperuricosuria. Allopurinol 150 mg b.d. improved the joint pain but was followed by several episodes of renal colic associated with progressive urinary frequency, nocturia and terminal dribbling. I.v. Urography and prostatic echography demonstrated left and right multiple small renal calculi and a large number of prostatic calculi.

Symptomatic treatment with no improvement.

On first examination, weight 80 kg, height 170 cm, BP 140/80. Complaints: suprapubic bladder pain, bilateral kidney tenderness, nocturia and dribbling. Blood test essentially normal except for elevation of ESR. Urine: pyuria and microscopic haematuria.

Diet: Low protein, fat free, low salt diet and force fluid by mouth. Antibiotics and antispasmodic drugs prescribed only for fever and severe pain.

2nd week of treatment: no more kidney pain, suprapubic pain better. Urine test: haematuria present, reduced proteinuria, pyuria absent. 3rd week of treatment: 4 uric acid stones expelled with colic. 4th week of treatment: 2 urine acid stones, no more kidney tenderness. Suprapubic distress and dribbling persist. At the 6th week the patient resumed work. During the 2nd cycle of isotherapy, in the 3rd week, the patient passed a total of 6 soft stones in 3 separate episodes, without colic. On laboratory examination these were found to be prostatic calculi. By the end of the 3rd isotherapy cycle a total of 16 prostate calculi had been expelled.

After 6 complete cycles of isotherapy the patient is practically completely recovered. I.v. urography demonstrated no evidence of the previous kidney stones. Prostate echography still positive for prostatic calculi, but reduced in number and size when compared with previous examination. ESR and urine down to normal values. After 11 months of observation the good result is maintained. The only treatment is 4 cycles of isotherapy per year and allopurinol 150 mg.

Bladder diverticulosis

Z.L., age 64, female, unmarried

Past history negative for major diseases. Menopause at age of 50. Now mild hypertension, overweight and burning dysuria. Patient treated with several courses of sulphonamide and antibiotics for recurrent cystitis. After two years developed severe allergy and all treatment discontinued. Cystography and cystoscopy revealed a diffuse diverticulosis of the bladder.

On first examination, weight 65 kg, height 150 cm, BP 160/90. Urine: Severe pyuria, haematuria, proteinuria, ESR elevated.

First cycle of isotherapy: no result.

2nd cycle of isotherapy: subjective amelioration. Urine: residual pyuria. Proteinuria absent. Haematuria present.

After 3rd and 4th cycle asymptomatic. Urine: no proteinuria no pyuria. Haematuria rarely.

After one year observation the patient takes 4 cycles of isotherapy per year. Regular urine test: asymptomatic, pyuria and haematuria rarely present.

Food allergy

M.P., female, age 20

Past history: no major disease. Admitted to hospital at the age of 6 for precocious puberty. Laboratory investigation was negative except

for oral glucose tolerance test which revealed a diabetic predisposition.

From onset of menarche several menstrual irregularities. Pelvic echography showed Stein-Leventhal syndrome and oral contraception was started; this caused a flare-up of the dermatitis.

The diet was severely restricted and at the age of 10 respiratory symptoms began to develop, with asthma and extensive atopic dermatitis. No treatment was successful.

After starting low calorie diet, skin tests or specific IgE antibodies positive for milk, egg, pork, starch, fish.

First examination, weight 74.4 kg, height 161.5 cm, BP 135/80. Severe generalized atopic eczema.

Blood test revealed hypothyroidism. Glucose tolerance test negative. RAST positive. PRIST test positive. Prick skin test positive for the majority of food stuffs. Patch testing considered too dangerous.

Kempner diet (boiled rice and fresh fruits) for 30 days reduced the weight by 10 kg but with poor results on skin condition.

Skin scales and urine were collected previous to diet and saved as mother tincture.

1st cycle of isotherapy: severe reaction from 1st to 4th week associated with asthma. Patient was started on fat free, salt free, high protein, sugar free diet (1000 calories/24 hours). At the end of the 1st cycle skin improvement was remarkable.

Three cycles of isotherapy were completed with no interval. Within 6 months skin was completely clear. Body weight 52 kg. Patient resumed normal diet except for milk, butter and cheese.

After one year: menstrual periods regular, body weight maintained, no skin allergy. PRIST + RAST negative. Patient continues four cycles of isotherapy per year.

Chronic glomerulonephritis

C.G., female, age 50, married, three pregnancies

Menopause at 48. Appendicectomy at 22. Ton-sillectomy performed at 23 years after severe episodes of streptococcal infection.

At the age of 25 patient developed hypertension: 200/100, irregular asymptomatic episodes of macroscopic haematuria, elevation of urea and blood creatinine. Admitted to hospital, the clinical picture was suggestive of chronic glomerulonephritis secondary to streptococcal infections. Symptomatic treatment was given with poor results.

At the age of 47 admitted to hospital with continuous asymptomatic haematuria, uraemia and severe elevation of blood creatinine, elevated proteinuria and i.v. pyelography was considered too dangerous. ESR was not performed but echography and kidney CAT revealed kidneys within normal limits. Kidney biopsy showed mesangial deposit of IgA. Patient was discharged with usual symptomatic treatment. After one year readmitted to hospital with no result. Two years ago the patient came to my observation.

At 1st consultation, BP 200/100, weight 101 kg, height 153 cm. Blood urea nitrogen (BUN) 0.80 (normal range 0.2–1.1). Creatinine 2.5 (normal range 0.6–1.1), ESR 70. Antistreptolysin titre (TAS) 600 (normal range up to 200), IgA 425.

For severe headaches skull X-rays, CAT and CT scan showed pituitary microadenoma which I considered irrelevant to the prescribing pathology. However, thyroid function tests indicated a severe hypothyroid condition. Salt-free, low sugar, low protein diet, plus lithium bromine reduced the weight by 10 kg in 40 days with little reduction of BP: 180/100. Persistent haematuria and elevation of elevation of TAS and ESR were treated symptomatically with isotherapy prepared with urine + throat swab.

After the 1st cycle haematuria disappeared, BP dropped to 160/100 and body weight reduced by a further 15 kg. BUN 65, creatinine 1.7, ESR and TAS normal. IgA 300 and general condition remarkably improved.

After 6 complete cycles of isotherapy the patient has no more haematuria, BUN 65, creatinine 1.20, BP 160/100.

The patient was admitted to hospital for hysterectomy for uterine fibroids, which was successfully performed. The pre-op work up was as above and she was considered by the doctors to have had a miraculous improvement when compared with previous admissions. The patient was invited to repeat kidney biopsy but refused; no conclusive proof can therefore be given of this exceptional result.

Conclusions

All the reported cases have been checked with laboratory investigations to ascertain if the obtained results had been achieved through placebo effect or isotherapy had an effective clinical therapeutic dimension.

The average number of courses of isotherapy administered varies from one to six, and the period of observation varies from six months up to three years. The best results had been obtained on the cases treated at the onset of symptoms and therefore not treated with the usual conventional drugs. Among the conventional medicines, the ones that have the most negative influence in isotherapy are corticosteroids, antibiotics and antiinflammatories.

Another observation worth making is that the patients treated with two or more cycles of isotherapy had gained an immunity to influenza. The percentage of increased immunity is around 50 if compared to the average number of the same sample of population during epidemics. This conclusion does not mean that isotherapy can be used as preventive therapy in influenza, but it is a matter for future investigation.

The economic aspect should also be taken into consideration. The cost of a complete course of isotherapy is one third when compared with a course of conventional drugs. It is very interesting that no patient goes to the doctor's surgery to demand medicines when perfectly fit, but in my experience quite often patients, having completed the treatment with satisfactory results, would return asking for further cycles.

The mechanism of action of isotherapy is unknown. It is a treatment where the infinitesimally small analogic picture of the disease itself and progressive immunity is obtained with a precise defensive desensitization. Isotherapy combines in one the splendid intuition of Paracelsus to transform a poison into a remedy and the scientific purpose of the homœopath who uses the smallest possible dose to secure a great therapeutic instrument.

Address for correspondence

Luciano di Nepi, MD
Viale di Trastevere, 82
00153 Rome
Italy